

Studies on Metal Chelates of Sulphamethazine Salicylaldimine

PRABUDDHA JAIN and KAMAL K. CHATURVEDI

Department of Chemistry, Holkar Science College, Indore

Manuscript received 14 July 1975; revised 7 November 1975; accepted 6 December 1975

Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with Sulphamethazine salicylaldimine (SUMTSA) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis. The absorption maxima were recorded. Infrared and magnetic susceptibility have been reported. They are found to be active against *E. coli*.

CONDENSATION products of sulphonamides with salicylaldehyde have been found to be good bacteriostatic^{1,2} and also good complexing agents³⁻⁶. Sulphamethazine salicylaldimine and its metal complexes are synthesised with a view to test the change in antibacterial activity on complexation. The results of analysis, absorption maxima, magnetic susceptibilities and infrared spectra have also been reported.

Experimental

All chemicals employed were of Analar grade. Synthesis and analysis of SUMTSA have been reported earlier⁷.

Ligand metal ratio was determined by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation and showed 2 : 1 complexation.

Isolation of complexes

SUMTSA in acetone was treated with an appropriate amount of metal acetate in acetone. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The resulting precipitate of the complex was filtered, washed with dry alcohol and dried.

The cobalt and nickel complexes are highly soluble in acetone and ethanol whereas the copper complex is comparatively less soluble.

Analysis

Copper was estimated iodometrically. Nickel was estimated with dimethyl glyoxime and cobalt as tetrapyridine cobalt dithiocyanate⁸ after removing the ligand.

Nitrogen was estimated by modified Kjeldahl procedure⁹ and Sulphur by Messenger's method.

Magnetic susceptibility and spectral measurement

The absorption spectra in solution was recorded in the region 320-950 nm using acetone as solvent with Beckmann spectrophotometer DU-2.

The magnetic susceptibility of the complex was determined at room temperature by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were applied using Pascal's constant¹⁰.

The infra red spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer model 237.

Results and Discussions

The results of analysis and physical properties are recorded in Table 1.

The analytical data given in Table 1 show that SUMTSA form 2 : 1 complexes with copper, nickel and cobalt.

Magnetic properties

Copper chelate has a magnetic moment value of 1.76 characteristic of a planer configuration with hybrid dsp^2 bonds¹¹. The nickel and cobalt chelates gave moment values corresponding to their free ions. The formation of weak covalent bonds resonating with ionic ones are thereby suggested. This suggest the formation of planer weak sp^2d bonds resonating with ionic ones.

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND ABSORPTION DATA OF SUMTSA COMPLEXES

Compound	Composition	Colour	m.p. °C	% N		% S		% Metal		μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} n.m.
				Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found		
Cu-SUMTSA	$(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})_2\text{Cu}$	Green	215	13.57	13.52	7.75	7.65	7.63	7.50	1.76	395
Ni-SUMTSA	$(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})_2\text{Ni}$	Yellow	198	13.64	13.44	7.93	7.96	7.15	7.12	3.51	325
Co-SUMTSA	$(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})_2\text{Co}$	Brown	205	13.62	13.55	7.91	7.85	7.18	7.10	4.42	310

Infra red spectra

On the basis of infra red spectra the intra-molecular hydrogen bonded chelate structure has been proposed for Sulphonamide salicylaldimines¹². On metal chelate formation, however, the two bands at 2625 cm^{-1} , 2592 cm^{-1} assignable^{13,14} to chelated OH involving N disappear. Also the strong band at 1640 cm^{-1} assignable to C=N stretch^{15,16} of SUMTSA is observed in complexes in the region 1650-1655 cm^{-1} . The observed shift obtained in C=N stretch after complexation suggests that azomethine nitrogen is co-ordinated to the metal ion. The absorption band at 1320 cm^{-1} only in metal chelates and not in SUMTSA is possibly a combination frequency of M-O and M-N stretches in metal chelates.

The band at 1260 cm^{-1} in SUMTSA may be assigned to phenolic C-O stretching. The bands near 1320 cm^{-1} in chelates may also be due to phenolic C-O stretching. This is indicative of M-O bond formation with oxygen of the -OH group of SUMTSA.

These observations led to the following conclusions:

- (1) In all complexes the azomethine nitrogen has taken part in the co-ordinate bond formation. As a result of this the bond order of carbon to nitrogen link is increased.
- (2) Disappearance of hydrogen bonded—OH in complexes and high frequency shift of the phenolic C-O stretch are the suggestive of M-O bond formation.

The bacteriostatic property of the complexes are compared against SUMTSA by the method described earlier¹⁷, against *Escherichi coli*. In all cases antibacterial activity was observed. Thus weight for weight complexes appear to be more potent than the parent compound.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (P.J.).

References

1. TAKEO TSUKAMATO and KENNOSUKE YUHI, *Yakugaku Zasshi*; 1958, **78**, 706, *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, **52**, 14561b.
2. TAKEO TSUKAMATO, Takeda Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd. Japan, 1960, 5766; *Chem. Abs.* 1961, **55**, 5879f.
3. R. R. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 385.
4. PRABUDDHA JAIN and KAMAL K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (in press).
5. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1975, **52**, 805, 1220, 1225.
6. P. RAY and A. K. MUKHERJEA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 604.
7. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (Communicated).
8. A. I. VOGEL, 'Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', Longmans Green & Co. Ltd. London 1959, IV 33-D, 461, 466.
9. M. ASHRAF, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 559.
10. P. W. SELWOOD, 'Magneto Chemistry', Inter Science Publishers Inc. New York, 1955, 92.
11. P. RAY and D. N. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **25**, 473.
12. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
13. L. J. BELLAMY, 'The I. R. Spectra of complex molecules' Methuen, 1964, 105.
14. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1270.
15. P. TEYSSEE and J. J. CHABETTE, *Spectro Chim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 1407.
16. L. E. CLOUGHERTY, J. A. SOUSA and G. M. WYMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 462.
17. K. K. CHATURVEDI, S. SIDDIQUE, B. K. AGARWAL and R. KAUSHAL, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1975, **37**, 85.